

RESEARCH ARTICLE

A brief history of a subversive future: cities of ecological entanglement

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Henri Lefebvre wrote of a future world turned upside down. This counter-narrative is an exploration of what that might look like and how that may come about. Written with scholar-activists in mind, this is a call to action for new modes of storytelling. As a proof of concept, this article offers fresh methodological and epistemological contributions in just transition scholarship. Transcending history, this speculative nonfiction story traverses a counterfactual future transpiring between 2025 and 2049. Here, present tense refers to 31 December 2049. However, the focus is on the ideas and struggles that provide the foundations that would make a utopian future possible. There is particular attention paid to the possible role speculative nonfiction scholarship could play. The story begins with an overview of its theoretical frame of ecopedagogy before delving into its methodological framework within speculative nonfiction that draws on backcasting and autoethnographic traditions. This future is grounded in historical precedent – both from literature as well my own lived experience. The second section provides a short overview of the motonormative imaginary that helped create the troubled cities we have today. What follows is not a *probable*, but a *possible* future. Here, the metacrisis is overcome through an explosion of veganic urban agriculture that upends the animal industrial complex – making way for a radical rewilding of cities and agricultural lands, as well as a revolution in inclusive democracy. Finally, I explore how the envisioned biophilic cities might transform our relationships with the more-than-human world, with one another and ourselves.

Keywords just transition counter-narrative • speculative nonfiction • post-car cities
• veganic urban agriculture • ecopedagogical imagination

Key messages

- Call to action for writing counter-narratives in academia to engage and motivate audiences to overcome the metacrisis.
- A proof of concept demonstration of how speculative nonfiction could be combined with backcasting and autoethnographies.
- Excite the imagination about the possibilities of post-car cities that embrace veganic agriculture.

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You never change things by fighting the existing reality. To change something, build a new model that makes the existing model obsolete.

— R. Buckminster Fuller ([Sieden, 2012](#): 313)

Imaginaries old and new

As the sun sets on 2049, it is perhaps a good time to take stock of just how far we have come. This article is an embellishment of remarks I made to a group of young scholars at the Earth System Governance conference in Nijmegen this year. This is a story about food, cars and power, but above all, our imagination. I will not be giving a blow by blow of recent decades. Here, I want to highlight the important role scholar-activists played in changing the narrative – which I argue, was essential for realising the Transition. To understand their role, we must recognise the hegemonic narratives they fought against, as well as the broader historical foundations and emancipatory struggles they were a part of. Finally, I want to address how changes to the urban fabric upended our relationships with one another, with other beings and with ourselves. Like all tales of history, this one cannot claim to be comprehensive or absolute: it is inherently flawed and blinkered; but one might argue that history books and future plans alike, are also works of *fiction* ([Barry and Elmes, 1997](#)).

For two decades, I felt like the proverbial square peg – never really able to find my niche. So having returned to academia, it was a revelation to meet the amazing imagination scholars at the Earth Systems Governance conference back in 2023. I had no ambitions of being a storyteller, but it became somewhat of a salvation. While my role in the Transition was all but imperceptible, working in solidarity with other scholar-activists, advancing new futures, nourished me to my core. I was infused with a new found confidence and sense of purpose and meaning, as each of us added a drop to the bucket of imagination that developed into the unstoppable tsunami of change that it became.

Take a moment to remember where we came from. Picture yourself alone, trying to repair a house – as a mob take it to pieces with sledgehammers. In 2023, that house was planet Earth. We were spending not double, not triple, but 30 times as much trying to wreck our planet as we did trying to preserve it ([UNEP, 2023](#)). This ‘metacrisis’ was the calamitous cluster-freckle of overlapping and intermeshed social justice and environmental catastrophes ([Misiaszek, 2015](#); [Bettache et al, 2020](#); [WMO, 2022](#); [UNEP, 2023](#); [Ripple et al, 2024](#); [Spratt, 2024](#); [WFP, 2024](#)).

What’s the use of having developed the science well enough to make predictions if, in the end, all we’re willing to do is stand around and wait for them to come true?

— F. Sherwood Rowland ([Brodeur, 1986](#))

At 195 cm, Sherry was indeed a towering figure. However, his gravitas stemmed from his science. In 1974, Sherry revealed the devastating impact caused by synthetic chlorofluorocarbons to the ozone layer (Molina and Rowland, 1974). The Nobel Prize-winning chemist was a tireless campaigner, frustrated by how climate science was being ignored for so long (Powell, 2019). Our lack of action was certainly not due to a lack of knowledge (UN, 1987) or technology (Lovins and Bethe, 1977). In response, other scholar-activists later called upon us to ‘push our analyses and actions beyond the state, beyond capital, and beyond the human via a broader anti-authoritarian perspective’ (Pellow, 2020: 296). In this light, I became intrigued by ecopedagogy – the logical extension of critical pedagogy. Much more than an educational paradigm, it encapsulated both my understanding of the matrix of domination that defined the problem (Collins, 2008), as well as a theory of change that moved my godless soul (Kahn, 2010; Shoaib et al, 2020; Slevin et al, 2020). The godfather of critical pedagogy was a Brazilian educator by the name of Paulo Freire. He felt it imperative that liberation came from below – for when the oppressed speak up en masse, the power of the people is mobilised, creating the conditions that make upending exploitative power structures possible (Freire, 1978; Kahn, 2010; Epstein-HaLevi et al, 2021).

For Paulo, liberation began with *conscientização*, or critical consciousness; for only when people had a deep understanding of the nature of their structural oppression would they have the motivation to act (Freire, 1978). As a white boy of privilege, my own critical consciousness was stirred at the age of 15. To escape high school, I spent 18 months with my dad in Indonesia. On one of many trips I took tagging along with his students around East Java, we ended up at this hotel at the foot of Mount Batu. An orangutan was kept in a cage by the pool. I named her after that mountain. Batu’s long black hands wrapped languidly around the thick steel bars of her concrete cell, eyes glazed over: not looking at me, but *through* me. I imagined how *I* might feel in that cell. Rationalising differences on speciesist grounds seemed utterly pedantic. As much as I wanted to break open that cage, I was not convinced Batu would have taken even one step out of her prison.

There were a cascade of tipping points that led us *into*, and a cascade of tipping points that led us *out* of the metacrisis – each littered with precedent. The infamous Powell Memo was one such trigger leading us in. Alarmed by the growing power of the labour, the civil rights and the environmental movements, a Big Tobacco lawyer by the name of Lewis F. Powell Jr. wrote a call to arms to the US Chamber of Commerce in 1971, entitled: ‘Attack on the American Free Enterprise System’ (Powell, 1971). Lewis called for free-marketeers to unite to thwart what Samuel Huntington later called the ‘excesses of democracy’ (Giroux, 2004: 3). To change the narrative, corporate leaders banded together to pour billions over 50 years into foundations, universities, networks of junk tanks, lobby groups and media outlets (Giroux, 2004: 3). The Heritage Foundation was one infamous junk tank that was founded two years later. In Ronald Reagan’s first cabinet meeting, he handed out copies of the Heritage Foundation’s 3,000-page how-to guide to his staff. Their efforts were so successful in mainstreaming this hardcore economic doctrine that I remember hearing Margaret Thatcher declare there was simply ‘no alternative’ (Brown, 2019; Giroux, 2004); a sentiment echoed in Francis Fukuyama’s proclamation of ‘the end of history’ (Fukuyama, 1992). While much of Brit-pop celebrated the election of Tony Blair’s Labour Government in 1997, Radiohead

was more circumspect. *OK Computer* was an album that transcended electoral politics, to opine on democracy more broadly – riffing on a wariness of technology and the bleak impotence of the individual in the face of corporate power (Tranmer, 2019). It evoked the disillusionment many of us felt.

[T]he future enters us in this way in order to be transformed in us, long before it happens.

— Rainer Maria Rilke (Rilke, 1993: 50)

Granted, some researchers carry more weight than others, but there is a rigour and reflection to scholarship that bestows a claim of authority. Thus, scholars have a power to legitimate or marginalise new ideas that can shift the Overton window (Biermann, 2014). In that sense, we are imagination gatekeepers. However, old ways of communicating environmental issues were ‘often fatalistic’, as they were stuck in the existing mechanistic paradigm that ‘preclude[d] the possibility of imagining something different’ (Epstein-HaLevi et al, 2021: 17). In this way conventional forecasting methods were of limited use because they presumed the very power structures that were stifling change would remain (Bibri, 2018; Nikolakis, 2020). I then learned about backcasting. It works differently – as it is not so presumptuous (Bibri, 2018; Nikolakis, 2020). This method begins by presenting a vision of what ought to be, then traces the steps needed to get there. The French urbanist, Henri Lefebvre, suggested we should *transduce* the contradictions between the world we want from the world we have (Lefebvre, 1970: 6). For Henri, this was not merely an analytical exercise, but one that took an active role in bringing a future into being (Lefebvre, 1970: 6). To bring the kind of gravitas needed to change minds, approaches like backcasting could ground possible futures in historical precedent (Mazzucato, 2021). Moreover, backcasting can help flesh out concrete strategies that could be implemented (Bibri, 2018; Mazzucato, 2021). However, backcasting methods used in traditional scholarship tended to be confined within conventional academic structures (Bibri, 2018; Nikolakis, 2020). When it comes to inspiring the reader’s imagination of possible futures, traditional nonfiction has its limitations.

Fiction engages readers in important ways non-fiction cannot. Reading fiction triggers the imagination, allowing us to conceptualize simulations of the real world and thus neurobiologically *experience* alternative realities.

— Estella Carolye Kuchta (Kuchta, 2022: 196–7; original emphasis)

For Trekkie Gene Roddenberry, ‘science fiction is a way of thinking, a way of logic that bypasses a lot of nonsense’ (Mission, 2019). Given sci-fi’s potential for conjuring up the future and offering counter-narratives (Schneider-Mayerson et al, 2020; Malpas, 2021; Mastrantonio, 2023), the author Ray Bradbury saw the genre as far from trivial, but ‘the history of our civilization birthing itself’ (Mission, 2019). As a parent, Bradbury’s chilling 1950 techno-dystopian tale of a virtual reality nursery gone frighteningly wrong, haunts me still. Speculative climate fiction began to come into its own in the 2020s (Robinson, 2020; Schneider-Mayerson et al, 2020; Varoufakis, 2020; Malpas, 2021). One such speculative fiction author, Kim Stanley Robinson, preferred utopias: for hope may be ‘fragile’, but it is also more ‘persistent’ (Milkoreit, 2017: 13). Ruth Levitas (2013) called for us to use utopia as a *method* of scholarship to push for more just futures. This was vital for developing the kind of critical hope that Paulo demanded (Freire, 1978).

Let us think the unthinkable, let us do the undoable, let us prepare to grapple with the ineffable itself, and see if we may not *eff* it after all.

— Douglas Adams ([Mission](#), 2019)

To harness this neurobiological potential of fiction in unleashing imaginations – without forgoing the epistemological gravitas of scholarship, I began exploring speculative nonfiction. However, some argued it created more problems than it solved. Feathers were ruffled when the likes of Hunter S. Thompson began to mess with journalistic conventions. One critic of such gonzo journalism was Dwight Macdonald, who claimed it was a ‘bastard form, having it both ways, exploiting the factual authority of journalism and the atmospheric license of fiction’ ([Macdonald](#), 1965). Another who shared Macdonald’s concern was Lyon Sprague de Camp, who was a prolific American author who wrote both nonfiction and sci-fi. As a utopian-dreaming exercise, de Camp questioned its usefulness for change in the ‘real’ world, as well as whether such flights of fancy could be tested or verified ([de Camp](#), 1980). For Lyon, the very integrity of scientific discourse was at stake ([de Camp](#), 1980). Other critics bemoaned the lack of specificity canvassed in such speculative nonfictions – such as in the works of Paul Mason’s *Postcapitalism* (2015), and Nick Srnicek and Alex Williams’s *Inventing the Future* (2015). Henri Lefebvre himself may well have wondered how fantastical scenarios relate to material conditions and path dependencies?

However, others saw its potential to reconcile such conundrums. They argued that through speculative nonfiction, we were able to ‘imagine new ways of *being* in the world’ ([Kuchta](#), 2022: 193; original emphasis). As was demonstrated, speculative nonfiction need not be antithetical to more conventional academic norms. While not only being able to give our readers a neurobiological *experience* of possible futures, such counter-narratives could be grounded in empirical data and logical reasoning. Elements of this approach have been used successfully to expand the imagination of the possible in education ([Kahn and Humes](#), 2009; [Shoaib et al](#), 2020), political theory ([Mason](#), 2015; [Nixon](#), 2020), in ‘social dreaming’ ([Kelley](#), 2002) and ‘visionary fiction’ ([Imarisha et al](#), 2015; [Robinson](#), 2020; [Varoufakis](#), 2020), but were also used to engage readers on an emotional level ([Markley](#), 2023). Transcending texts, this approach was also used in documentaries ([Çarka](#), 2024). In a similar vein, speculative thought experiments were used to challenge the very foundations of science itself ([Latour](#), 1993). While the natural sciences tend to avoid ambiguity, speculative nonfiction uses it as a weapon. Here, the reader must draw on their own knowledge and experience to fill in the gaps. Julia Martin found that through this ‘potentially inspiring and versatile’ approach, she could reach new audiences ([Martin](#), 2019: 219). Although, I would acknowledge, this was not universally the case ([Haraway](#), 2016b). I came to concur with Julia that this ‘genre-bending’ medium allows ‘stylistic choices to be a significant vehicle of meaning, offers a standpoint for situated truth claims while making ample room for ambiguity and ambivalence, and places trust in the imagination as a way of knowing’ ([Martin](#), 2019: 219). It could also be more fun to write ([Martin](#), 2019: 219).

The effectiveness of speculative nonfiction depended upon how grounded it was – both in evidence, but also in providing actionable strategies. Injecting an academic rigour through backcasting was an effective approach in speculative fiction ([Robinson](#), 2020; [Varoufakis](#), 2020) and speculative nonfiction alike ([Fullerton](#), 2015; [Hawken](#),

2017; Raworth, 2017; Mazzucato, 2021; Hopkins, 2023; Bolton, 2024; Çarka, 2024). By drawing on scientific literature, case studies and historical analyses, they were able to make their futures more compelling. While being agnostic to any particular genre or discipline, they could offer a tangible roadmap forward. With limitations of space and time, no piece of writing can be all things to all people. Just as fiction excels at making ideas come alive, nonfiction helps to ground them. In Olympic terms, we might think of nonfiction as weightlifting and fiction as figure skating. Speculative nonfiction must be competitive in both.

[I]t matters what stories we tell to tell other stories with; it matters what knots knot knots, what thoughts think thoughts, what descriptions describe descriptions, what ties tie ties. It matters what stories make worlds, what worlds make stories.

— Donna Haraway (Haraway, 2016a: 12)

Perhaps one of the more inspiring stories about the future came from Simon Amstell's 2017 utopian mockumentary, *Carnage: Swallowing the Past* (Amstell, 2017). In this prophetic satire set 50 years into the future, a world is depicted that had yet to be realised – one where kindness and compassion reigned. While the young appeared happy and carefree, older folk are in therapy – for they *remember*; their guilt for eating animals haunts them still. This shift in perspective allowed a certain kind of *reflection* on what was the predicament of that era. What was once just *dinner*, suddenly becomes a reminder of our own complicity in a 'bloodbath' of epic proportions (Amstell, 2017).

[E]ating is an agricultural act.

— Wendell Berry (Berry, 1990: Part III, Ch. 7, para. 3)

As a farmer and poet, Wendell was reminding us that we cannot divorce the food on our plates from the farms they came from – however much our culture wanted us to. That is where these counterfactual approaches come in. They work on our minds differently – allowing us to see the world we take for granted with fresh eyes. Hegemonic narratives entrench norms such that they are made invisible (Adams, 2021; Bolson and Shapiro, 2017); counter-narratives however, challenge them – helping to upend majoritarian tales and foreground marginalised perspectives (Kahn and Humes, 2009; Monno, 2014). Such approaches were vital for creating the protected space for radical imaginations to thrive (Dyke et al, 2018). The point is not always about whether or not these futures are probable – or even likely (Milojević and Inayatullah, 2015: 152); for we must remember that not everyone saw a future for telephones or the internet when they were first floated (James, 2015). What matters is how these visions facilitate a transition towards a preferred future that meets 'our needs and desires' (Milojević and Inayatullah, 2015: 152).

As a child, I was fond of drawing from a bird's perspective. I began writing stories in a similar way to help contextualise our everyday lives on the streets within the larger social and ecological structures that we exist in. But as no good story is complete without a protagonist, I began searching for one. Just as C.W. Mills highlighted, it is in the very dynamic between the micro and the macro that helps us understand the structures we are entangled in – as well as our possible role in reproducing or challenging them (Mills, 1959). Richard Kahn echoed this sentiment when describing the ecopedagogical

imagination (Kahn, 2010). Demonstrating the intimacy of the self/world dialectic was also a cornerstone for some reflexive forms of autoethnographic praxis. Here there was a 'back-and-forth movement between experiencing and examining a vulnerable self and observing and revealing the broader context of that experience' (Ellis, 2007: 14). With some reluctance, I had found my character ... albeit not the one I had in mind.

Carmageddon

To the extent that the contours of the future city can be outlined, it could be defined by imagining the reversal of the current situation, by pushing to its limits this inverted image of the world upside down.

— Henri Lefebvre (Lefebvre, 1996: 172)

Last night, I heard the blackbirds sing as the sun faded over the horizon. I picked up a book from the street library while I waited for a tram to go by. I felt the lush lippia underfoot between the tracks as I walked back from the communal shed. I tipped my hat to our resident permaculture guru. Carey Kneebone was tending to her beloved sugar snap peas the way you might to a newborn. I picked a bunch of grape tomatoes and an aubergine for dinner before turning to head home. As I did, a red tricycle flew by, taking me back to another time, another world.

'Shut up, shut up!' Becky was addressing the birds. Singing honeyeaters would start up at dawn. Back in the late 1980s, when Becky was just five, a car left her with traumatic brain injuries. While my neighbour back in Australia was not quite as fond of birdsong as I was, we both shared a love for riding our bikes down to the beach. Back in the summer of 2014, she rode her electric tricycle down to the beach almost daily. While I battled through traffic, Becky took her fire-engine-red trike on the footpath. It may not have been legal, but no police officer would dare fine her; she was a force to be reckoned with.

The cities of the 1980s that Becky and I grew up in, were nothing like the cities of today. For much of my life, cities were all about building more roads, more car parks, more drive-thrus – and dormitory suburbs for days. There was a road built in China that was 50 lanes wide. But one day, those 50 lanes tuned into a parking lot (Poon, 2015). Gridlocked, some 85 million people slept in their cars for 12 days straight (Poon, 2015). So not only was the car responsible for the life-crippling mental and physical disabilities Becky suffered, they could also be inconvenient. While China's G4 behemoth was perhaps a little larger than most, the imagination that created it was one that persisted in most cities throughout the globe at that time (Dennis and Urry, 2009; Molotch, 1976).

Yet, I do have fond memories of driving on the open road through the New Mexico desert in a baby blue Chevy Impala. It was straight out of a Hunter S. Thompson novel. But alas, I was only eight, so I was in the back seat with my sister – and it was only Fanta that I was tripping on. Driving for some was their most 'cherished right' (Furness, 2010: 7). Many behind the wheel were soothed in the rhythmic act (Béquet et al, 2020). That sense of control and mastery over nature is what many relished most (Béquet et al, 2020). In 1909, the Italian futurist artist Filippo Marinetti exalted in 'the beauty of speed', delighting in the way the car embodied danger, violence and militarisation: an all-out assault on feminine sensibilities – anything he deemed to be remotely emasculating (Ladd, 2011: 39). Fillippo revelled in how this new private vehicle symbolised one of the most undemocratic forms of transport imaginable (Ladd, 2011: 39).

But when cars were first introduced to our streets, they were guests that had no more right to be there than a bike or anything else. Car sales were stymied by bad press. The automobile was derided for more than just trampling over bodies (Dennis and Urry, 2009; Ladd, 2011; Miner et al, 2024). In 1927, an English philosopher by the name of Cyril Joad noted that ‘motoring is one of the most contemptible soul-destroying and devitalising pursuits that the ill-fortune of misguided humanity has ever imposed upon its credulity’ (Ladd, 2011: 39). Cyril likened the noise to that of a regiment of soldiers who ‘had begun to suffer simultaneously from flatulence’ (Ladd, 2011: 39). The German sociologist, Werner Sombart, was bitter too: howling that ‘one person was permitted to spoil thousands of walkers’ enjoyment of nature’ (Ladd, 2011: 18; original emphasis). For those wealthy enough, the car offered an escape from the grime and soot. But Cyril scoffed at this: ‘From the country they are completely cut off; they cannot see its sights, hear its sounds, smell its smell, or enjoy its silence’ (Ladd, 2011: 18).

If you’re not careful, the newspapers will have you hating the people who are being oppressed and loving the people who are doing the oppressing.

— Malcolm X (Kuroski, 2016)

The car industry responded by withholding their vast advertising dollars until newspapers changed their tune (Ladd, 2011). Pedestrians on the street started being referred to as *jays* or *jay walkers* – a racist trope to refer to ‘lazy’ African Americans (Ladd, 2011). In 1925, Los Angeles made jaywalking a crime (Ladd, 2011). Giving the car exclusive rights to the street was a watershed moment, and marked the beginning of decades of obfuscation, denial and delay tactics (Ladd, 2011) – eerily similar to that used to protect Big Tobacco by Lewis and his mates in the decades to come (McDowall, 2022).

While working on a 35-year campaign to stop a highway ploughing through an urban wetland, I was confronted with just how entrenched motonormativity was (Walker and te Brömmelstroet, 2025). We were walking in the footsteps of the Dutch Provo movement’s war on cars. Through his radical magazine, *Provo*, Roel van Duijn was instrumental in fuelling radical imaginations of a post-car Amsterdam. Soon after being elected to council in 1971, Roel began receiving death threats (Dekker, 2022). This was on account of him pushing for such horrifying initiatives as free public bikes. Not without some irony, van Duijn was abducted and literally driven out of the country (Dekker, 2022). The well-known right-wing gang was never charged. Since the mid-1960s, the police had their eyes elsewhere. The persecution of the Provo movement had the full backing of the state. In a campaign against the Apocalypse jalopies, the Japanese artist, Yoshio Nakajima, took inspiration from the French surrealists. In Schiedam, at the Gallerie Honger, Yoshio poured red liquid and water over his bare chest, while the ‘safe traffic magician’ (*veiligverkeermagiër*) proceeded to smash a car to pieces (Dekker, 2022: 223). This was to symbolise the blood spilt and tears shed for children struck down by the ghouls on wheels. This was one of many *crash happenings* Yoshio took part in. He was then arrested for the 13th time that year – before being deported (Dekker, 2022: 223).

As a child of the 1970s, car-centric urbanism was ubiquitous to me. Growing up in Australia, devoting our streets to cars was rarely questioned. This gave me the impression that most people wanted such cities. I was wrong: car-centric cities had no such broad consensus (Walker and te Brömmelstroet, 2025). Colleagues called this

kind of collective delusion about perceived popular support, *pluralistic ignorance* (Walker and te Brömmelstroet, 2025). The persecution of the Provo movement was testament to how effectively opposition was suppressed (Dekker, 2022). Having crushed dissent, tech-bro-oligarchs weaponised their immense influence to promulgate their cyberpunk fantasies as utopias (Marx and Managh, 2022). It is much easier to go along with something we disagree with when we think everyone else supports it (Walker and te Brömmelstroet, 2025). Pluralistic ignorance helped to explain a great deal about the disconnect between what people *wanted* and what people *got* across a raft of urban, social and environmental policies (Prince and Schiff, 2008; Steinberg and VanDeveer, 2012; Capstick et al, 2015; Stokes, 2020; Orr et al, 2023; Schlozman and Rosenfeld, 2024).

The heedlessness with which the public still crosses the busiest streets is beyond belief; and many parents let their children use the street as a playground, as if ... automobiles simply don't exist.

— German motoring magazine, 1909 (Ladd, 2011: 21)

History has shown that many behind the wheel soon developed a taste for deliberately running over people – and critter alike (Ladd, 2011). Anyone from my generation who dared cycle on the road felt the wrath of motorheads (Giddings, 2019). In February, 2023, in broad daylight, Dr Michael Mammone was struck on his bike from behind. Completely stationary, the cyclist was waiting at a traffic light – *in the bike lane*. The CCTV footage I saw shows him being thrown just shy of the traffic lights on the other side of the intersection (Hurford, 2023). The driver turned his car around to where Michael lay. Armed with a BB gun and a knife, the driver continued his assault. Michael later died in the very emergency ward where he worked (Hurford, 2023). There was no such footage of the incident that left my neighbour with severe head injuries. The launch of the video game, *Carmageddon*, at the turn of the century laid bare just how successful the automobile lobby was in taking over our streets: players were rewarded for hitting pedestrians (Ladd, 2011: 22). The narrative was total.

Could there have been a more befitting symbol of our *mastery over nature*? Dominating our public space, cars were the manifestation of our extractivist, individualistic, competitive and wasteful tendencies that characterised our cities then (Molotch, 1976; Dennis and Urry, 2009; Ladd, 2011; Beatley, 2017). Such cities alienated us from our inherent entanglements to one another (Beatley, 2017), and to the greater ecology we are a part of (Carson, 1962; Sheldrake, 2020). Some argued that we all have an intrinsic need to connect with nature (Biro, 2005; Beatley, 2017). Thus, the harm we had caused to nature (IPCC, 2023), to non-human animals (Clinton et al, 2018) and to one another (Bettache et al, 2020) resulted in a great schism in our hearts (Joy, 2010).

A cascade of tipping points

Most of the times, when we have little to nothing to eat, I struggle to get my children to sleep at night ... They ask for food and I try to distract them, telling them stories until they're asleep, then I look at them and pray for a better life until I get stolen by sleep.

— Aishah Sadaah (Oxfam, 2021)

Along with her four young children, Aishah found herself in this desperate situation having fled war-torn Yemen in 2018. After 24 hours without food, the body begins feeding on itself – first carbohydrates and then fats, before drawing on its protein tissue (Brink, 2016). You then begin feeling cold and weak. At this stage, your muscles, lungs and heart shrink. Concentration becomes more difficult and you become more prone to irritation. In the next stage, you might start hallucinating or go into convulsions. Finally, with no energy to pump, your heart will give out (Brink, 2016). Beyond such wars, droughts were also a common cause. Mega-droughts that had global ramifications had history: the Dust Bowl hitting North America in the 1930s, the African Sahel Drought of the 1970s and 1980s, and the Paraná–La Plata Basin Drought in South America between 2019 and 2021 (FSIN, 2024). Between 1980 and 2018, drought-stricken areas increased each year by an area roughly the size of Slovakia: 50,000km² (Chen et al, 2025). In 2023, the number people facing catastrophic (IPCC/CH Phase 5) levels of famine was unprecedented (FSIN, 2024). This was double that of the previous year (FSIN, 2024). Due to war, droughts, inflation and inefficiencies, such famines became more prevalent and persistent across the globe through the 2020s and 2030s (FSIN, 2024). Aishah’s family was not alone.

When the Wall came down in Berlin in 1989, the walls went up in Cuba. Severed from trade, Cubans had to go solo. Having relied almost entirely on food imports, the sanctions hit hard. As was done in many countries during the Second World War, Cuba began its programme of severe food rationing (Altieri et al, 1999). People then started growing food just about anywhere they could – backyards, patios, balconies and rooftops (Altieri et al, 1999: 132). As synthetic pesticides were banned within city limits, growers resorted to more traditional methods (Fukuoka, 1978; Mollison, 1988; Altieri et al, 1999). With limited resources, growers used what organic waste they could get their hands on. To protect cruciferous vegetables such as broccoli from the caterpillar *Pluella xylostella*, Havana’s growers used diluted quantities of *Bacillus thuringensis* and the nematode, *Steinernerma carpocapse* (Altieri et al, 1999: 136). These agroecological traditions understood that pests and diseases were symptomatic of ecological imbalances (Altieri et al, 1999: 136). A healthy plant was considered to be more resilient. Therefore, the solution was to ensure the soil was healthy and to balance the ecology of the garden (Fukuoka, 1978; Mollison, 1988; Altieri et al, 1999; Videle, 2023).

The main issue is that the right to have access to every building in the city by private motorcar, in an age when everyone possesses such a vehicle, is actually the right to destroy the city.

— Lewis Mumford (Mumford, 1963: 11)

People planted out every vacant lot, every nook and cranny. This was next level guerrilla gardening across cities, across continents. Yet more was demanded. Given that half of many cities was devoted to cars (Newman and Kenworthy, 1989; Ellen McArthur Foundation, 2015), people started giving those carbon croakwagons a dirty look. In the early decades of the century, budding post-car cities were hiding in plain sight. As the first woman to be elected mayor of Paris in 2014, Ann María Hidalgo adopted Carlos Moreno’s idea of the *15-Minute City* to help curb car dependency (Moreno et al, 2021). Although heavily contested at the time (Nello-Deakin, 2023), Ann’s use of cheap tactical urbanism was turbo-charged through the COVID-19

pandemic of the early 2020s – and was later made permanent (Fabris et al, 2023). Back in Ann's country of birth, Miguel Anxo Fernández Lores, was elected as mayor of Pontevedra, Spain, in 1999. Miguel soon abolished street parking, lowered speeds to 30 km, and limited private vehicle access to residents, emergency vehicles and deliveries (that were confined to certain hours). By 2021, car-free zones had been expanded, and car-traffic was reduced by 90 per cent (Khreis and Nieuwenhuijsen, 2021; McAskie, 2021; Pazos-Otón, 2024). In the wake of each new food crisis, these kinds of approaches surged globally. This was not rocket surgery (Jacobs, 1961; Gehl, 1971; Harvey, 2012; Pfeifer, 2013; Beatley, 2017; Bruntlett and Bruntlett, 2018; Kern, 2019; Doheim et al, 2020; Broto, 2021; Moreno et al, 2021; Schwanen, 2021; Sarnow and Tiedemann, 2022).

Gardening is the most ... defiant act you can do.

— Ron Finley (Weston, 2020)

While those pioneering cities were critical in showing the world what was possible, this Transition would not have happened if it were not for the guerrillas. They usually began small. Much to the chagrin of the asphalt aristocrats, pot plants started springing up kerb-side. But such efforts were often met with vandalism (Weston, 2020; Lawrence, 2024). As neighbours got together in their community gardens, pluralistic ignorance was composted into fruitful conversations about how they could put food on the table for their kids. An all-out assault on the auto-centric narrative was mounted on the airwaves and on the streets. Inspired by the French Situationists, their protests were festivals of delight – mixing critical mass gatherings and guerrilla gardening, with musical *crash happenings* (Dekker, 2022). Planter boxes got bigger. Some became Mad Max barricades – growing horns, and being reinforced with old bricks, concrete and scrap metal.

Time spent parking increased as planter boxes flooded our streets. It soon became simply quicker to take a tram or hop on your bike. As large and fast vehicles were no longer tolerated on our streets, we had to get smarter and more local. Freight was largely moved underground (Visser, 2018), while emergency services took to the skies (Sigari and Biberthaler, 2021). Streets became inviting places to walk again. Like dandelions, pop-up cafes, markets and fairs grew through the cracks of the fast-evolving jungle of concrete. Drawing on the Dutch movements of old, grassroots counter-plans were developed. They did not stop at bike plans, but made counter-policies that placed inclusivity at the core of food (Artmann and Sartison, 2018; Roberts and Geels, 2019; Lacy, 2000), housing (Nelson and Schneider, 2018; Durning, 2021; Geissel, 2022; Koch, 2022; Bua and Bussu, 2023), work (Lacy, 2000; Weeks, 2011; Clark, 2019), and energy (Burke, 2018; Riofrancos, 2020; Sarnow and Tiedemann, 2022; Sovacool et al, 2023). As the popularity of these grew, councils began adopting them – or stepping up with their own initiatives. For some, letting go of the car was like letting go of part of themselves (Furness, 2010). But through these changes, attitudes began to shift. Old narratives gave way to new realities. In 2028, Pontevedra removed jaywalking laws from the books. As other cities soon followed, police officers had to find other things to do.

The once-almighty allure of the automobile began losing its sheen. It was not the first time that a cultural icon was given the boot. In 2012, Australia's plain packaging law on cigarettes replaced the chiselled jaw of the Marlborough Man with graphic

images of throat cancer and gangrene. Needless to say, Big Tobacco's Tinder rating took a hit. The war on cars drew on the war on smoking playbook, facilitating a similar shift in perceptions. Billboards were satirised, ads subverted and parodied (Reilly, 2013; Kingsmith, 2016). Over time, car commercials came to appear more absurd than the parodies. Old narratives lost their grip.

Initially, people just grew for their own families, but as more and more smelly space-invaders were taken out of cities, gardens expanded exponentially. This allowed some growers to sell their surplus at the farmer's market. Especially in the early years of the lingering food shortages, it was common for produce to be shared with those most in need – just as growers in Havana had (Altieri et al, 1999). Cooperatives formed alongside food-sharing initiatives and community-assisted agriculture (Davine, 2017; Pettygrove, 2018; Clark, 2019; Federici, 2018; Roelvink et al, 2015). Growers were getting organised. Community toolsheds popped up on just about every corner, soon followed by free stores. Ditto with street libraries – often filled with the latest veganic horticulture books. Inspired by Forum Groningen and the Helsinki Central Library Oodi, sophisticated community-resource centres with everything from books to 3D-printing and cafes, sprang up. These helped to provide quality indoor public space that encouraged human flourishing – irrespective of one's bank balance. Coupled with mutual aid initiatives, the shareable economy was kicking in, minimising costs and resource consumption. Neighbourhoods became communities.

There's really no such thing as the 'voiceless'. There are only the deliberately silenced, or the preferably unheard.

— Arundhati Roy (Roy, 2004: para.4)

Democracy in the first decades of this century was not healthy (Giroux, 2004; Klein, 2015; Brown, 2019; Broto, 2021; Duarte, 2022). As some feminist urban scholars noted, it was rare for disadvantaged groups to be actively engaged in these so-called *participatory* processes (Broto, 2021). Such endeavours had largely been a ruse – as some are made to feel 'more welcome than others' (Broto, 2021: 2). They were often used to 'manufacture ... technocratic' objectives (Broto, 2021: 2) and 'reproduce inequalities and buttress the status quo' (Stapper and Duyvendak, 2020: 1). That mirrored my own experience in 2001 with Dialogue for the City Perth. There, I joined a thousand others – who were largely white, largely middle class – in a big shed. Even then, very little of the collective imagination that we developed in that exercise came to pass.

Power concedes nothing without a demand.

— Frederick Douglass (Douglass, 1857)

As we became more self-sufficient, corporate chains began to corrode. Transitioning to more sustainable modes of being necessitated a broader reconfiguration of economic models (Göpel, 2016). As social movements grew in number and confidence, they began demanding more. This coincided with a raft of experiments in democracy and regenerative ecological economics more broadly (Raworth, 2017; Howard-Vyse et al, 2022; Olk et al, 2023). Many began on a very local scale within protected spaces that offered a nursery environment that could be scaled gradually (Lai, 2023; Maher et al, 2023). Some grassroots organisations pushed for ecological justice that centred the needs of the most marginalised (Red Nation, 2021; Warlenius, 2017). These took

off in various forms – from general strikes (Gallas, 2020), collective visioning (Innes, 2010), people’s budgets (Hernández-Medina, 2010), citizens’ assemblies (Farrell and Suiter, 2019), micro-utopias (Lydon and Garcia, 2015), boycotts (Beck, 2018), as well as broad-scale divestments and sanctions (Davidson and Gross, 2018). In 2015, Black Lives Matter (BLM) led the People’s Budget Coalition to platform an alternative budget for Los Angeles that put vulnerable people first (Barrett and Safransky, 2024). This strategy caught on, where increasingly more detailed and sophisticated counter-budgets were developed for cities. Building on this people’s budget movement, the most powerful examples came from coalitions that involved a plurality of interests that put the needs of the most vulnerable first (Barrett and Safransky, 2024).

Citizens’ assemblies and participatory budgeting were instrumental. Initially, many conformed to antiquated voluntary models but, over time, they became increasingly more inclusive. In 2000, São Paulo elected its first woman as mayor. Before being elected, Marta Suplicy was best known for her candid sex advice on TV. Marta led a new approach to people’s budgets. Two thirds of the city’s total budget – across all sectors – was decided not by regular politicians, but by elected delegates (Hernández-Medina, 2010). In this system, a privileged man would need 20 votes to be elected, while an Indigenous person or someone with a disability only needed a single vote. Due to their weighed voting system based on levels of disadvantage, almost half of the delegates elected came from one of nine vulnerable groups (Hernández-Medina, 2010). Starting back in São Paulo in 2029, this approach was combined with various inclusive sortition models to be piloted across dozens of cities globally (Farrell and Suiter, 2019). In the early years, these were shadow-budgets like that run by People’s Budget Coalition in America, but as they grew in popularity, pressure mounted on governments to adopt them. Budgets began small, but as they proved themselves, they grew. With the increasing popularity of such assemblies, they became ensconced within a new democratic culture. Such examples that reflected this ecopedagogical imagination were refined and scaled to tremendous effect.

Ingraining such deep democracy into the culture of our everyday lives began breaking down barriers. A toxic media culture that ravaged our democracy (Gearhart et al, 2019) began to give way to this more inclusive approach (Wainwright, 2017; Sarnow and Tiedemann, 2022). This helped to dissolve old power hierarchies, leading to a decolonisation of knowledge (Bhambra and Nişancıoğlu, 2018) and atmospheres alike (Warlenius, 2017). Eventually, this helped to transcend what Arlie Russell Hochschild (2016) called our ‘deep story’ – our story about parties and country, the story we tell ourselves about who we are. Such stories make for myopic imaginations that do not lend themselves well to democracy or circumventing the wicked problems we faced (Freire, 1978; Mezirow, 1991).

I have watched chimpanzee children, after the death of their mothers, show behavior similar to clinical depression in grieving children – hunched posture, rocking, dull staring eyes, lack of interest in events around them ... Sometimes, in this state of grieving, chimpanzee orphans – like Flint and Kristel – die.

— Jane Goodall (Bekoff, 2007: xiv)

As gardens in the cities evolved, our diets did too. Our entire notions of what constituted *food* changed. Eating is a visceral experience that connects us to the Earth

in a fundamental way. An attack on our food feels personal (Joy, 2010). So changing diets did not come easily. Challenges to the animal industrial complex were met with fierce resistance – and not just from the conglomerates. Some were lucky to escape with their life; others were less lucky. In 2015, a slaughterhouse driver drove into Megan Russell after she gave water to pigs on the truck. Russell did not live to offer another pig a drink (Bugga, 2020). After a life battling cattle ranchers in the Amazon, a 73-year-old nun by the name of Dorothy Stang found herself on a list. Two gunmen took her out with six bullets (Tautz, 2019). Carnism was baked into the system (Joy, 2010). In the early 2000s, animal justice activists competed with al-Qaeda for the FBI's attention (Best and Kahn, 2004).

Our goal is to remove uncivilized people from civilized society.

— Chris Christie (Best and Kahn, 2004: 3)

As New Jersey's attorney general at that time, Chris Christie was referring to the SHAC7. As one of the 'uncivilised' seven, Jake Conroy spent four years in prison for having knocked down the stock value of a vivisection corporation. For Chris, it was perfectly civil to transplant genetically modified pigs hearts into the necks of baboons. But Jake was the 'thug' (Best and Kahn, 2004: 3). For fear of going back to maximum security, Jake told me in Luxembourg that he no longer worked with non-human animal justice groups.

Nobody in the world, nobody in history, has ever gotten their freedom by appealing to the moral sense of the people who were oppressing them.

— Black Panther, Assata Shakur (Shakur, 1987: 138)

The vegan world we know today did not happen overnight – it was a process. The work that comrades like Jake did in highlighting injustice and cruelty was vital. In an old slaughterhouse in 2015, I heard Melanie Joy tell us about how eating non-human animals had come to be seen as 'natural', 'normal' and 'necessary' (Joy, 2010). But having your food system on your street was confronting for some; not everyone had the stomach for it. Most people were fond of non-human animals, yet still ate them. When they were reminded of this, it is understandable that such cognitive dissonance would cause discomfort. To make a traditional Christmas dinner, Estonians used to stuff a mixture of oats and fresh blood into a pig's intestine. After making *verivorst*, or blood sausage, for the first time, our friends went vegan soon after. For the kids who grew up playing with chickens and goats in their yard, they were friends, not food. Parents began feeling increasingly uncomfortable slicing the throat of Simba and Momo.

Another scholar-activist at that same conference painted us a vision of a vegan utopia. Tobias Leenaert was a self-described Belgian pragmatist who was adamant that a vegan world was all but inevitable – given enough time (Leenaert, 2017). It is worth remembering that it took the Brits a good two centuries to get over their suspicion of the menacing red tomato (Alexander et al, 2017). For a time, the Yanks fertilised their crops with lobsters (Alexander et al, 2017). Progress was slow, but as people began eating fewer animals, appetites for plant proteins grew. The practicalities of getting our protein from plants was simply easier, used less land and less water (Alexander et al, 2017; Poore and Nemecek, 2018). It also happened to be less bloody.

This is to say that change was well underway before the pandemics hit. When the avian influenza B3.13 genotype A(H5N1) was detected in a dairy cow in the United States in 2023, there was some concern (Nguyen et al, 2024). But in March 2027, alarm bells rang loud when H5N1 was discovered in humans in Standpoint, Idaho. Found to have been transmitted through unpasteurised milk, H5N1 infections spread throughout the United States over the ensuing months. Given the state of health coverage in the country, many cases went unreported, leaving it to spread and mutate into more virulent strains, pushing hospitals to the brink. In the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic, four international bodies (the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, the United Nations Environment Programme, the World Health Organization and the World Organisation for Animal Health) joined forces to develop the One Health framework in 2022 (FAO et al, 2022). This was a holistic approach that recognised that human health was intimately entwined with the health of non-human animals and ecosystems more broadly (FAO et al, 2022). This framework was instrumental in implementing immediate crackdowns on the sale of animal flesh and, later, stricter welfare and health standards, along with bans on advertising and cuts to subsidies, albeit happening much later in some countries (Morach et al, 2021; Siegrist et al, 2024). As 2.4 million died globally in the first year, fear rose and sales of chopped liver, legs and breasts fell. By 2030, plant protein became just as accessible in the cities as their bloody alternatives (Morach et al, 2021). Other pandemics followed in Belgium in 2033 and most recently in Argentina in 2041. With fears escalating, the vegan transition went into hyperdrive. As plant proteins became more abundant, available and affordable, eating animals became increasing harder and more expensive. It was simply easier to eat plants.

Biophilic cities

The worst thing, worse than the physical danger, is the emotional toll ...
Pigs down on the kill floor have come up and nuzzled me like a puppy.
Two minutes later I had to kill them – beat them with a pipe. I *can't* care.

— Ed Van Winkle, hog-sticker at Morrell Slaughterhouse plant, Sioux City, Iowa (Dillard, 2008: 1; original emphasis)

Beyond being dangerous physically, there is also the ‘perpetration-induced traumatic stress’ (PITS) and the *moral stress* that Ed refers to (Grušovnik and Blaznik, 2022). Ending the animal industrial complex induced a number of positive feedback loops. People no longer suffer in slaughterhouses. Most people are inherently empathetic towards non-human animals from an early age (Grušovnik and Blaznik, 2022). Therefore, denialism and psychological distancing were necessary for us to swallow the cluster-fudge of carnism (Joy, 2010; Muller, 2018). As Melanie Joy (2010) quizzed us, ‘why do we love dogs, eat pigs and wear cows?’ While some were imprisoned for hurting dogs, others like Ed were *rewarded* for beating pigs to death with a pipe (Dillard, 2008: 1). On account of a plant-based diet, we are generally healthier and live longer (Selinger et al, 2022). Our mental health is better too: we no longer have to endure the moral whiplash involved in loving and eating animals. As is often the case, our heads tend to follow our feet (Joy, 2010). So once people stopped eating animals, we began to open our hearts (Joy, 2010).

My socks were wet. I felt the bass pulsate through my skin as I dug in the soil on the outskirts of Dryandra, Western Australia. It must have been sometime around the turn of the century. Covered in mud, we planted trees in a torrential downpour as the DJ threw down the beats. It was a tree planting rave; and it was glorious. Planting trees was one of the most nourishing things I felt I could do. I knew many of my fellow diggers from years past, working on the remote Aboriginal reserve of Pia. We were following in the footsteps of the organisation's founder. Richard St Barbe Baker was an English forester who worked with the Masai on an extraordinary rewilding project in Kenya in the 1920s. This gentle soul had a vision that was as much about people as it was about trees. St. Barbe's utopia was one where we were 'surrounded by fruit and nut orchards and live free from disease and enjoy leisure, liberty and justice for all, living with a sense of their one-ness with the earth and with all living things' (Baker, 1979: 118–19).

The United Nations designated the 2020s as the decade of Ecosystem Restoration (Svenning, 2020). Its aim was 'to prevent, halt, and reverse the degradation of ecosystems', going on to say it could 'help to end poverty, combat climate change and prevent mass extinction' (Svenning, 2020: 657). By revolutionising our food systems, we created the space for rewilding on the scale necessary (Svenning, 2020; Monbiot, 2022; Pettorelli, 2022). Planting out derelict land was just the beginning. It was only when the steel and rubber contraptions were pushed out, that cities really started to bloom (Dennis and Urry, 2009). Reclaiming as much as half a city from the automobile was quite profound. Greening streets, roofs and walls, cities were kitted out in their finest greens. Letting the soil breathe again opened up new possibilities beyond food production and biodiversity (Monbiot, 2022). Integrating agroecology into the very fabric of our cities made flooding almost a non-issue (Mahmoud et al, 2022; Pettygrove, 2018). After we diversified and decentralised our crops, food production increased (Altieri and Funes-Monzote, 2012). Per square metre, we can produce up to 370 times as much plant-based protein as we could from animals (Poore and Nemecek, 2018). Bacteria-based protein sources have taken that to extremes (Monbiot, 2022). Food *waste* is now a prized resource. Organic methods of pest and weed control helped bring back soil health, thus increasing the quality and quantity of yields (Monbiot, 2022). The demise of animal agriculture allowed us to reclaim almost 70% of all arable land from the animal industrial complex (Steinfeld et al, 2006: xxi). As a biomass, humanity makes up just 0.01% of life on Earth. Yet we were responsible for wiping out half of all plants and 83% of mammals on the planet (Greenspoon et al, 2023). Until quite recently, the non-human mammals remaining were enslaved, eaten or enslaved and eaten (Greenspoon et al, 2023). Epic rewilding projects have provided us with the carbon sinks we desperately needed. As methane has a shorter life cycle than carbon dioxide, our dietary transition had an arguably more immediate impact on the climate than the energy transition – just as Robert Goodland and Jeff Anhang said it would 40 years ago (Goodland and Anhang, 2009). Feedback loops can work wonders.

It has been almost a century since Rachel Carson (1962) so eloquently articulated just how entangled we are in the broader ecosystems of the Earth. It took time, but in the 2020s and 2030s we phased out harmful pesticides and herbicides – some containing forever chemicals (PFAS). Since then, birthweights are up, cancer rates are down (Flesher, 2023). Reclaiming our air and water has increased the health of people and ecosystems alike (IPCC, 2023). When I say health, I mean these

changes brought physical, cognitive and emotional benefits (Flesher, 2023; Gillis and Gatersleben, 2015; York and Wiseman, 2012). Gardening has been known to be therapeutic – especially for those on the fringes (York and Wiseman, 2012). It raises our mood, and reduces our stress, depression and anxiety (York and Wiseman, 2012). I learned this having spent four years working on a permaculture farm. On that one-hectare city lot, most of what we grew was social capital. Through the act of nurturing plants, people began to look after themselves more – as well as those around them. Tilling the soil and harvesting healthy produce fed a collective identity, an *us* that people could feel proud of (Gillis and Gatersleben, 2015; York and Wiseman, 2012). Through this solidarity, gardening cultivates healthy egos and communities, fostering confidence and resilience (Gillis and Gatersleben, 2015; York and Wiseman, 2012). All this has allowed us to relate better, be more productive and even heal faster (Gillis and Gatersleben, 2015; York and Wiseman, 2012). Working with such a clear and noble purpose gave people enormous motivation (Gillis and Gatersleben, 2015; York and Wiseman, 2012). Our desperate need for food security drove the Transition and now our food system is more productive and more resilient than ever. This had a democratising effect that gave us a power over our food that we had not had before. Sovereignty is not just about self-sufficiency, but human dignity (Altieri and Funes-Monzote, 2012). Some had long argued that this very act of reconnecting with nature, of cultivating our biophilia, was the key to the Transition (Artmann, 2023; Roberts and Geels, 2020; Whitburn et al, 2020). Bringing birdsong back to our streets has lifted moods worldwide (Gillis and Gatersleben, 2015). Except Becky's, of course. Birdsong is not for everyone.

Feeling the texture of soil between your fingers provides a direct connection to the earth. It is one which can involve all your senses – actively. To paraphrase the great troubadour, Tom Waits, the things that are slow to grow are sometimes the most worthwhile. I must have sung that 'Little Man' song to my son a million times (Waits, 2006). Gardening can often be slow and deliberate, where there is need to pay careful attention to the smallest imperfection in a leaf. For some, simply admiring the intricate delicacy of a flower is an experience of mindfulness (Wood et al, 2022). Decades ago, Marc Bekoff asked us to 'rewild our hearts', where we can become 'reenchanted with nature' and nourish 'our sense of wonder' (Bekoff, 2014: 5). These ideas are echoed in Indigenous concepts like *Ubuntu* (Chibvongodze, 2017) and in the religious teachings of Jainism (Kumar, 2021). Having this interaction with the soil helped us rewild our hearts, such that the idea of *himsa* (violence) became alien.

Our struggle makes us human

Justice is what love looks like in public.

— Cornel West (Mills, 2020)

In the crisp New England autumn of 1995, Emily waited her turn. Ahead she would see others move through the swing doors. Suddenly, Emily turned and bolted. It may have been the smell of blood from the kill floor. Emily managed to hurl her 680 kg body over a 1.5 m fence and run into the forest around Hopkinson. As a cow, Emily was *property*. She was *owned* by the slaughterhouse, A. Arena & Sons.

Locals gave her hay and sent the police in the wrong direction. This allowed Emily to elude her pursuers for 40 days and 40 nights, before she was eventually brought to a sanctuary (Joy, 2010: 135–7). Cities have taken on a new sense of justice, love and liberty. If asked what freedom means to me now, I do not think of *Homo economicus*, I think of Emily.

If you are neutral in situations of injustice, you have chosen the side of the oppressor. If an elephant has its foot on the tail of a mouse and you say that you are neutral, the mouse will not appreciate your neutrality.

— Desmond Tutu (Brown, 1984: 19)

It was not biologically possible for the rate of extraction to have continued as it was in the 2020s (Kuchta, 2022). There was only so much planet to exploit and burn (UNEP, 2023). Change was inevitable. The only questions were about *when*, *what* and *how*. While the Transition was momentous, it was not entirely unpredicted. Henri was on point to suggest the transformation would come about through changes to the city (Lefebvre, 1996). Henri and Paulo long understood the latent power of those who had been most marginalised (Freire, 1978; Lefebvre, 1996). Others recognised the potential of urban agriculture for broader transformations (Hovorka et al, 2009; Tornaghi, 2017; Artmann and Sartison, 2018; Roberts and Geels, 2019; Gulyas and Edmondson, 2021; Lang, 2021; Dona et al, 2021; Royer et al, 2023), the role post-car cities could play (Dennis and Urry, 2009; Baehler and Rérat, 2020; Doheim et al, 2020; Verkade and Brömmelstroet, 2022), and the potential of cascading tipping points (Meldrum et al, 2023). Brought on by a convergence of climate impacts, pandemics, economic pressures, technological innovations and galvanised through social movements, urban agriculture did indeed turn our world upside down.

These were the gnarly tsunamis we can all point to. But beneath the surface, there were tectonic shifts at play that made those waves possible (Lacy, 2000; Xie et al, 2011; Geissel, 2022; Bua and Bussu, 2023; Iacopini et al, 2022). Scholar-activists played a role, for they knew that if the stories we tell are not challenging the hegemonic discourse, they legitimate it. It was not enough to fight the system, to critique the dominant narratives fuelling the metacrisis and present better alternatives. To shift the Overton window, we had to present these critiques, and these alternatives in new and compelling ways (Raven and Stripple, 2021). Speculative fiction was incredibly useful in pushing our imaginations forward. But speculative nonfiction was able to make those imaginations irresistible. In hindsight, we pulled a reverse-Powell: we changed the narrative by saturating the media, think tanks, unions, networked advocacy groups and universities with counter-narratives imbued with *conscientização* and critical hope (Freire, 1978).

When describing his ideal city back in 2016, Tim Beatley wrote of how greater contact with plants and animals would ‘feed our need for wonder and meaning’ (Beatley, 2017: 227). Mission accomplished? Cities are far greener, more compassionate and more just than they were while I was growing up. Now, *Homo sapiens* are not the only species that have ‘the right to live and thrive in cities’ (Beatley, 2017: 227). Yet oppression and exploitation still linger in some quarters, and our climate remains fragile; there is much work still to be done. As scholars, as activists, as human beings, we must continue push the envelope. In the midst of the apocalyptic 2020s, I would often ask myself if was doing enough. Would I be able to look my son in the eyes

in the years to come, and say that I did what I could: that I did not go quietly into this good night? I urge this new generation to keep pushing. For as Vijay Prashad declared, it is our struggle that makes us human (Prashad and Barat, 2022).

Our destiny exercises its influence over us even when, as yet, we have not learned its nature: it is our future that lays down the law to our to-day.

— Frederick Nietzsche, 1878 (Nietzsche, 1996: preface 7)

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